

FACTORS INFLUENCING CITIZENS' SATISFACTION WITH REAL PROPERTY TAX ADMINISTRATION IN SANTA CRUZ, DAVAO DEL SUR**Remy S. Taporoc, LPT**

Barangay Local Government Unit of Tagabuli, Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0233-7347>**Ronie G. Panes, DPA**

Professor, University of Southeastern Philippines, Mintal Campus, Davao City

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4785-8552>**ABSTRACT**

This study investigated the factors influencing the citizens' satisfaction with the administration of the Real Property Tax (RPT) in the Municipality of Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur, since administrative practices, such as information accessibility, payment system efficiency, and accountability measures, are crucial factors that influence individuals' perceptions of government effectiveness. Through the use of a structured questionnaire, data were collected from 63 real property taxpayers. These data were then analyzed through the application of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and descriptive statistics. The study methodology utilized was quantitative, descriptive-exploratory. The study determined the factors influencing the citizens' satisfaction in RPT administration and identified six principal dimensions which are: service delivery efficiency, the accuracy and fairness of RPT assessment, the accessibility of information and personnel, the transparency and accountability in RPT utilization, public participation and policy responsiveness, and the overall perceived governance efficacy. The six-factor model accounted for 71.377% of the total variance, signifying a robust and significant structure. The results show how important it is for municipal governments to be transparent and focused on the needs of their citizens in order to improve local tax administration, build trust among citizens, and develop local revenue governance. These findings provide actionable insights for local government entities aiming to enhance fiscal sustainability and promote equitable governance. The study aimed to furnish empirical evidence to support evidence-based decision-making, policy improvement, and enhanced transparency and accountability in real property tax administration.

Keywords:

Real Property Tax, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Administration, Satisfaction, Republic Act No. 7160, Republic Act No. 12001

INTRODUCTION

Real Property Tax (RPT) has long been regarded as the most effective and significant revenue source for local governments. A city or municipality that effectively manages its RPT would be able to finance essential services, maintain modern infrastructure, and deliver public goods. All of these factors are crucial to individuals' daily lives and their perceptions of local government. Ait Lhassan et al. (2022) established that perceived ease of use, together with the perceived usefulness and the website design, significantly influence customer satisfaction regarding the digital transformation of tax administration in Morocco. However, the other two factors, namely perceived confidence and perceived quality, adversely affect taxpayers' expectations. Further, a significant and stable revenue stream for local governments to provide essential public services is the real property tax (RPT). Communities' public service quality, quantity, and reliability indicate quality of life. Local governments need consistent funding to provide services. RPT taxes land and building ownership and occupation. This tax dates back to ancient times when land and its products were most precious, according to Hou (2020). The study of Vartašová et al. (2019) revealed that the Slovak Republic's real estate tax does not provide enough funds for territorial self-government to function independently. However, it is a tax with significant room for improvement in the future, particularly if more fundamental changes are made to its structure. Berry (2021) found that property taxes are the main source of revenue for US municipalities. This should be an ad valorem tax. The tax is fair and accurate only if local assessors do a good job of valuing property. Cifuentes-Faura et al. (2024) claimed that local government officials are accountable to citizens, who are increasingly demanding

greater transparency in light of their tax contributions. Their research findings indicate that the most transparent towns garnered more global tax revenues.

The Local Government Code of 1991, or Republic Act No. 7160, along with the Real Property Valuation and Assessment Reform Act of 2024, known as Republic Act No. 12001, empowered local governments in the Philippines to evaluate and levy real property taxes. It made RPT a vital part of municipal and city governments' work and a key way for local governments to be financially independent. Hassan-Tahil et al. (2024) determined that acknowledging the varied backgrounds and experiences of personnel is crucial when assessing the effectiveness of the Sulu Provincial Assessor's office's real property tax instruments. Zaragoza et al. (2020) shown that property taxes constitute an element of land governance policies, procedures, and institutions reliant on a robust land administration system, an efficient property market, and solid legal rights. Additionally, using rising property values as a source of revenue is a novel concept that allows property owners and developers to collaborate for the common benefit. The special assessment tax, also known as a special levy, allows the government to recoup its infrastructure investment costs by deducting a percentage of the land's value. Even though it has been in the Philippines' Local Government Code for a long time, it remains underutilized, and its full revenue potential has yet to be realized (Samantela & Maquiling, 2024).

Gutierrez et al. (2025) found that property assessment processes in Oriental Mindoro, Philippines, were only partially implemented, hindered by obsolete methodologies and insufficient training of assessors, thereby compromising accuracy. Consistent enforcement of penalties was the main reason for compliance, while income level and general awareness efforts had little effect. Technology made processing faster and payments more on time, but its full benefits were not realized since it was not always used. The Municipality of Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur, finances its municipal services through local taxes such as the real property tax. Historically, the RPT was the primary source of income. One strategy to improve fiscal performance is to modernize tax assessment and collection. Davao del Sur's provincial agencies and programs also promote open and participatory government through citizen service charters and town hall meetings. (Provincial Government of Davao Del Sur, 2025).

This study used a quantitative, descriptive-exploratory approach to evaluate what factors affect individuals' satisfaction with real property tax administration in Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur. The data were gathered solely from municipality residents who are paying real property taxes, employing a structured survey questionnaire that evaluated essential aspects such as citizen satisfaction and transparency regarding RPT administration services, service delivery efficiency, fairness and accuracy of RPT assessments, accessibility of information and personnel, availability and clarity of tax policies and procedures, public disclosure of collected RPT funds and their utilization, and the clarity and justification for tax rate adjustments. Non-random sampling was employed to select residents of the municipality who pay real property taxes, ensuring that the data accurately reflected the opinions of the most pertinent respondents. An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) identified citizen satisfaction structures in real property tax administration. The average satisfaction across parameters was summarized using descriptive statistics.

The objective of this study is as follows:

1. Determine factors influencing citizens' satisfaction with real property tax administration in Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur?

METHODOLOGY

The study's methods are covered in this chapter. It covers the research design, data sources, sampling method, data collection instrument, study protocol, and statistical analysis. This study used a quantitative, descriptive-exploratory research method to dig deeper and better comprehend the factors and elements under consideration to produce more accurate results.

The study employed primary data from 63 respondents who own and pay property taxes in Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur. To collect the necessary data, this study used a researcher-created questionnaire with 30 Likert-scale items to capture taxpayers' perceptions and experiences of satisfaction and transparency in real property tax administration. Their responses were compiled, summarized, and subjected to statistical analysis through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to discern the fundamental constructs of citizen satisfaction. Additionally, descriptive analyses were performed to evaluate the extent of citizen satisfaction.

A researcher-developed questionnaire with 30 items was designed to assess real property taxpayers' perceptions and experiences regarding the real property tax administration. A five-point Likert scale ranging from "Very Satisfied" to "Very Dissatisfied" was employed to quantify responses. The RPT administration's satisfaction

and perceived governance efficacy were not well captured by current techniques, prompting the deployment of researcher-made instruments (South, 2022). The elements were based on literature published between 2015 and 2025 on citizen satisfaction and involvement, local government, and public service transparency (Firman et al., 2024).

This study employed non-random selection to choose 63 real property taxpayers having firsthand experience in the municipality's RPT payment process. Because it enabled the researcher to focus on respondents with direct experience with RPT administration and transparency, non-random sampling was selected. It ensured that the collected data were pertinent and reflected the most informed opinions (Etikan & Bala, 2017). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to determine what factors affect citizen satisfaction with Real Property Tax (RPT) administration services. According to Watkins (2018), this method is beneficial when the researcher does not presume a preconceived structure and is interested in investigating how measurement items naturally group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides the analysis and interpretation of the aggregated data.

In accordance with the data presented in Table 1 below, which presents the results of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, the chi-square value is 1359.027. Additionally, there are 435 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000 ($p < 0.05$), which indicates that the correlation matrix exhibits a substantial deviation from the identity matrix. Due to the fact that these data provide evidence that underlying components exist, it can be concluded that the sample that was used for the study was suitable, and that exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was an adequate method of analysis. In light of the findings, the sample size that was applied in this investigation is adequate for conducting exploratory factor analysis (EFA).

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.848
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1359.027
	df	435
	Sig.	.000

Table 1. KMO and Bartlette's Test

Analysis of the variance percentage in Table 2, referred to as the overall Variance Explained Table, reveals that the first factor accounts for 13.136% of the overall variance. It signifies that it accounts for a substantial percentage of the dataset's variability. The study indicates that the second factor represents 12.530% of the variation, the third factor 12.43%, the fourth factor 11.545%, the fifth factor 10.893%, and the sixth factor 10.840%. The initial element is the primary contributor to the identification of the variation, whilst the sixth factor exerts the least significant influence.

The six identified indicators jointly account for a total variance of 71.377% as per the table. These six parts account for the majority of the underlying variance in the dataset, offering a significant representation of the data's structure. These attributes pertain to the service efficiency delivery, the accuracy and fairness of RPT assessment, the accessibility of information and personnel, the transparency and accountability in RPT utilization, the public participation and policy responsiveness, and the overall perceived efficacy of governance. The model's practical significance is evidenced by the efficacy of these six-factor solutions in accurately representing the data's underlying structure and fulfilling the criteria for factor validity.

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	13.216	44.054	44.054	13.216	44.054	44.054	3.941	13.136	13.136
2	2.730	9.101	53.154	2.730	9.101	53.154	3.759	12.530	25.666
3	1.657	5.523	58.678	1.657	5.523	58.678	3.730	12.433	38.098
4	1.502	5.008	63.686	1.502	5.008	63.686	3.464	11.545	49.644
5	1.282	4.274	67.960	1.282	4.274	67.960	3.268	10.893	60.537
6	1.025	3.416	71.377	1.025	3.416	71.377	3.252	10.840	71.377

Table 2. Total Variance Explained

The scree plot was utilized to visually represent the number of factors affecting public satisfaction and openness in the management of real property taxes. As illustrated in Figure 1 below, the point above the debris or break, excluding the break itself, signifies the quantity of items to be retained. The Scree plot as well as eigenvalues demonstrated a deviation from linearity, aligning with a 6-factor solution.

Figure 1. Scree Plot

Service Delivery Efficiency. Table 3 presents the six items categorized under the first dimension, service delivery efficiency, together with their respective loading coefficients. The item "The RPT payment procedure is simple and easy to follow" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.845. The statement "The RPT payment process is simple and easy to follow" had a loading coefficient of 0.764. The statement "The RPT administrative office location is convenient to access" had a loading coefficient of 0.733. The statement "The waiting time before being served for RPT matters is short" had a loading coefficient of 0.707. The statement "Staff provide complete and timely support when I inquire about RPT" received a loading coefficient of 0.591. The statement "Staff are efficient in completing RPT transactions" had a loading coefficient of 0.580.

Service delivery efficiency is an important part of public service excellence. It shows how well processes, people, and systems help people complete transactions with little effort and delay. Table 3 shows that the main reason Real Property Tax (RPT) services are efficient is the simple, straightforward payment process. The item on how easy it is to follow the RPT payment process has the highest factor loading, indicating a substantial effect on the construct. The administrative office's accessibility and lower wait times further underscore the importance of convenience and time efficiency in establishing positive service attitudes. Even though aspects related to staff have lower loadings, they are still important parts of overall service delivery efficiency, as they directly affect user trust and satisfaction. These results are consistent with other researchers' findings. They say that streamlined processes, easy access, and responsive staff are important factors in how people perceive the efficiency and quality of service in public sector organizations (Osborne, Radnor, & Nasi, 2015).

Table 3. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Service Delivery Efficiency

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
1	The RPT payment procedure is simple and easy to follow.	.845	Service Delivery Efficiency
2	The RPT payment process is simple and easy to follow.	.764	
4	The RPT administrative office location is convenient to access.	.733	
5	The waiting time before being served for RPT matters is short.	.707	
6	Staff provide complete and timely assistance when I inquire about RPT.	.591	
3	Staff are efficient in completing RPT transactions.	.580	

Accuracy and Fairness of RPT Assessment. Table 4 presents the six components categorized under the second dimension, which pertains to the accuracy and fairness of RPT assessment, together with their respective loading coefficients. The statement "I believe the current tax assessment reflects the fair market value of my property" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.784. The statement "I perceive the RPT amount I pay to be equitable compared to others in the community" received a loading coefficient of 0.692. The statement "My RPT assessment is accurate and reflects the correct property details" received a loading coefficient of 0.632. The statement "The process of appealing or correcting an RPT assessment is fair" had a loading coefficient of 0.629. The statement "The RPT administration ensures that all property owners are treated equally in assessment" received a loading coefficient of 0.552. The statement "I have confidence in the accuracy of the RPT records kept by the administration" had a loading coefficient of 0.504.

Taxpayers' trust and approval of local tax systems depend on the accuracy and fairness of Real Property Tax (RPT) assessments, which directly affect how people see equality and validity. As shown in Table 4, the most important indicator of this dimension is taxpayers' view that the assessed value equals the fair market value of their property. It shows how important it is for valuations to be accurate in influencing people's ideas of justice. The perceived fairness of property details and their comparison with those of other community members further underscores the importance of open, consistent evaluation methods. Also, a fair appeals or corrections process makes taxpayers feel they are getting fair treatment, while equal treatment of all property owners and trust in the accuracy of the records help the institution's credibility. Nathan et al. (2024) showed that perceived equity in tax processes influences taxpayer attitudes and behaviors, particularly their willingness to comply, which increases when they believe others are contributing equitably and regard the system as fair. The OECD (2025) also found that fair appeal processes and equal treatment are vital for strengthening procedural justice in tax administration. It helps people trust and have faith in how institutions work.

Table 4. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Accuracy and Fairness of RPT Assessment

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
8	I believe the current tax assessment reflects the fair market value of my property.	.784	Accuracy and Fairness of RPT Assessment
10	I perceive the RPT amount I pay to be equitable compared to others in the community.	.692	
7	My RPT assessment is accurate and reflects the correct property details.	.632	
9	The process for appealing or correcting an RPT assessment is fair.	.629	
11	The RPT administration ensures that all property owners are treated equally in assessment.	.552	
12	I have confidence in the accuracy of the RPT records kept by the administration.	.504	

Accessibility of Information and Personnel. Table 5 presents the nine components categorized under the third dimension, which pertains to the accessibility of information and personnel, together with their respective loading coefficients. The item "The step-by-step procedures for RPT assessment and payment are clearly explained" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.777. The statement "I understand how my property is appraised for RPT purposes" received a loading coefficient of 0.751. The statement "RPT policies are easily accessible to the public" had a loading coefficient of 0.740. The statement "The guidelines for granting RPT exemptions or incentives are publicized and clear" had a loading coefficient of 0.727. The statement "Information on how to pay RPT is easy to find" had a loading coefficient of 0.700. The statement "The RPT office has sufficient staff to handle inquiries and transactions" achieved a loading coefficient of 0.679. The statement "I can easily contact the appropriate personnel to clarify RPT concerns" had a loading coefficient of 0.676. The statement "RPT personnel are approachable and willing to assist" received a loading coefficient of 0.645. The statement "The RPT administration utilizes multiple channels for information dissemination" received a loading coefficient of 0.625.

One important part of good Real Property Tax (RPT) administration is making sure that information and staff are easy to find. It affects taxpayers' understanding, confidence, and capacity to meet assessment and payment requirements. Table 5 shows that the most important factors are the clarity of step-by-step instructions and taxpayers' grasp of how property evaluation works. It shows how important it is to have clear and easy-to-understand information in public financial management. The substantial loadings for policies open to the public, clear rules for exclusions or incentives, and payment information that is easy to find show that openness and

access to information are key to how accessible something seems. Also, the friendliness, helpfulness, and responsiveness of RPT staff are important parts of this dimension, underscoring the importance of human interaction alongside access to information. Using more than one way to communicate also shows how modern expectations for service delivery are open to everyone and focused on the needs of citizens. These results align with recent literature suggesting that transparent information, accessible personnel, and multi-channel communication foster trust, mitigate information asymmetry, and enhance satisfaction with tax administration and other public services (Morgeson, VanAmburg, & Mithas, 2019).

Table 5. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Accessibility of Information and Personnel

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
19	The step-by-step procedures for RPT assessment and payment are clearly explained.	.777	Accessibility of Information and Personnel
21	I understand how my property is appraised for RPT purposes.	.751	
18	RPT policies are easily accessible to the public.	.740	
20	The guidelines for granting RPT exemptions or incentives are publicized and clear.	.727	
14	Information on how to pay RPT is easy to find.	.700	
15	The RPT office has sufficient staff to handle inquiries and transactions.	.679	
17	I can easily contact the appropriate personnel to clarify RPT concerns.	.676	
13	RPT personnel are approachable and willing to assist.	.645	
16	The RPT administration utilizes multiple channels for information dissemination.	.625	

Transparency and Accountability in RPT Utilization. Table 6 presents the four items included under the fourth dimension, transparency and accountability in RPT utilization, together with their respective loading coefficients. The statement "The reports on RPT fund utilization are easy to understand to the average citizen" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.817. The statement "The RPT administration publicly discloses the total amount of RPT collected" received a loading coefficient of 0.774. The statement "The RPT administration provides regular updates on the status of RPT-funded projects" received a loading coefficient of 0.770. The statement "Information on where the collected RPT funds are spent is made public" received a loading coefficient of 0.764.

For local government financing to be seen as legitimate and for people to trust it more, Real Property Tax (RPT) funds must be used in an open and accountable manner. The most important thing in Table 6 is that reports on how RPT funds are used should be easy for citizens to grasp. It shows that transparency works best when information is not just shared but also easy for everyone to understand. The high loadings for making total RPT collections public, providing regular updates on RPT-funded projects, and publishing comprehensive spending information underscore the importance of open fiscal communication and regular reporting. These procedures let people keep an eye on how their tax dollars are spent and ensure public money is handled properly. According to recent research, clearly reported local taxes with accountability systems make citizens more involved, lead them to think the government is doing a better job, and increase their trust in public institutions (Cuadrado-Ballesteros, Mordán, & García-Sánchez, 2017).

Table 6. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Transparency and Accountability in RPT Utilization

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
24	The reports on RPT fund utilization are easy to understand by the average citizen.	.817	Transparency and Accountability in RPT Utilization
22	The RPT administration publicly discloses the total amount of RPT collected.	.774	
25	The RPT administration provides regular updates on the status of RPT-funded projects.	.770	
23	Information on where the collected RPT funds are spent is made public.	.764	

Public Participation and Policy Responsiveness. Table 7 presents the two components categorized under the fifth dimension, public engagement and policy responsiveness, along with their respective loading coefficients. The item "There is a public consultation or opportunity for feedback before RPT rates are adjusted" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.853. The statement "The reasons and justification for any change in RPT rates are clearly communicated" had a loading coefficient of 0.690.

Public participation and policy responsiveness are essential elements of good Real Property Tax (RPT) governance, as they indicate the degree of taxpayer involvement in decision-making and awareness of policy modifications. Table 7 shows that the best indicator of this dimension is the presence of public consultations or opportunities to comment before changes are made to RPT rates. It shows how important it is for local fiscal policymaking to be open and participatory. Clear disclosure of the reasons and explanations for changes in RPT rates further promotes policy responsiveness by helping citizens understand the rationale behind actions that directly affect them. These behaviors help people see justice, openness, and responsibility in the process. Recent research has shown that these factors can increase people's trust in the government, lead them to accept tax policies, and make them see the government as more legitimate (Fung, 2015).

Table 7. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Public Participation and Policy Responsiveness

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
27	There is a public consultation or opportunity for feedback before RPT rates are adjusted.	.853	Public Participation and Policy Responsiveness
26	The reasons and justification for any change in RPT rates are clearly communicated.	.690	

Overall Perceived Governance Efficacy. Table 7 presents the three items categorized under the sixth dimension, overall perceived government efficacy, together with their respective loading coefficients. The statement "The RPT administration is effective in managing real property taxation" received the highest loading coefficient of 0.821. The statement "I have confidence in the capability of the RPT administration to serve the community" had a loading coefficient of 0.820. The statement "The RPT administration demonstrates good governance in its operations" had a loading coefficient of 0.766.

Overall perceived governance efficacy is how taxpayers view the Real Property Tax (RPT) administration's capacity to perform tax functions competently and in line with sound governance principles. Table 7 shows that the strongest signs of this dimension are people's beliefs that real property taxes are being managed well and their trust in the administration's ability to serve the community. It shows how important institutional competence and performance are in shaping public opinion. The strong loading for the item on good governance further shows that effectiveness is tightly linked to following rules such as accountability, openness, and responsiveness. These perceptions indicate that when citizens witness regular performance and effective administrative methods, they are more inclined to regard the RPT system as genuine and reliable. This conclusion aligns with contemporary governance literature, which underscores that perceived efficacy and administrative capability are essential factors influencing public trust, contentment, and confidence in local government institutions (Bouckaert & Van de Walle, 2017).

Table 8. Transformed Matrix Featuring a Cluster of Attributes Pertaining to Overall Perceived Governance Efficacy

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
28	The RPT administration is effective in managing real property taxation.	.821	Overall Perceived Governance Efficacy
30	I have confidence in the capability of the RPT administration to serve the community.	.820	
29	The RPT administration demonstrates good governance in its operations.	.766	

CONCLUSION

The study determined the factors influencing the satisfaction of the real property taxpayers of the Municipality of Santa Cruz, Davao del Sur. The study finds that citizen satisfaction is the key to how well people think the Real Property Tax administration is doing its job. The identification of six interrelated dimensions illustrates that effective Real Property Tax governance transcends mere revenue collection, including: service delivery efficiency, the accuracy and fairness of RPT assessment, the accessibility of information and personnel, the transparency and accountability in RPT utilization, public participation and policy responsiveness, and the overall perceived governance efficacy. When these attributes are in place, taxpayers have greater confidence in the RPT administration, which strengthens their ideas of trustworthy governance.

The study suggests that the local government make RPT payment and assessment processes easier and more digital, thereby making services more efficient and reducing wait times. To ensure assessments are fair and accurate, the rolls need to be updated regularly, assessors need to be trained continuously, and appeals processes need to be enhanced. The municipality should ensure that information is available on multiple platforms and that there are enough staff to respond promptly to taxpayer concerns. Publishing concise, citizen-friendly reports on RPT collections and spending, together with regular updates on RPT-funded initiatives, can make things more transparent. Finally, making public consultations a regular part of the process and clearly explaining why tax rates are changing can help policies be more responsive and keep citizens involved.

REFERENCES

- 1) **Ait Lhassan, I., Bedraoui, O., & Akhannich, O. (2022).** The impact of digital transformation on the satisfaction of tax administration users in Morocco during the Covid-19 pandemic: An empirical study. *European Journal of Management Issues*, 30(1), 48-57. Retrieved from <https://hal.science/hal-03649249/>.
- 2) **Berry, C. R. (2021).** Reassessing the property tax. Available at SSRN 3800536. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3800536.
- 3) **Bouckaert, G., & Van de Walle, S. (2017).** Trust in public administration. In E. Ongaro & S. Van Thiel (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of public administration and management in Europe* (pp. 329–344). Palgrave Macmillan. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-55269-3_17.
- 4) **Cifuentes-Faura, J., Benito, B., & Guillamón, M.-D. (2024).** The Influence of Transparency on Municipal Taxation: An Empirical Analysis. *Administration & Society*, 56 (5), 653-682. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/00953997241239024>
- 5) **Cuadrado-Ballesteros, B., Mordán, N., & García-Sánchez, I. M. (2017).** Is local financial transparency associated with higher levels of citizen trust? *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 83(4), 761–784. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852315582130>
- 6) **Etikan, I., & Bala, K. (2017).** Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 00149. Retrieved from <https://medcraveonline.com/BBIJ/sampling-and-sampling-methods.html>.
- 7) **Firman, F., Sumatono, S., Muluk, M. K., Setyowati, E., & Rahmawati, R. (2024).** Enhancing citizen participation: The key to public service transparency. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(1), e2937-e2937. Retrieved from <https://ojs.journalsdg.org/jlss/article/view/2937>.
- 8) **Fung, A. (2015).** Putting the public back into governance: The challenges of citizen participation and its future. *Public Administration Review*, 75(4), 513–522. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12361>.
- 9) **Gutierrez, S., & De Guzman, B. (2025).** Determinants of Real Property Tax Collection in Oriental Mindoro: A Basis for Strategic Policy Reforms. *Aloysian Interdisciplinary Journal of Social Sciences, Education, and Allied Fields*, 1(9), 589-601. Retrieved from <https://journals.alloysianpublications.com/index.article/view/397>.
- 10) **Hassan-Tahil, N., & Asiri, M. (2024).** Impact of real property tax tools of Sulu Provincial Assessor's Office: employees' perspectives. *SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY AND HUMAN EXPERIENCE*, 1(1), 1-14. Retrieved from <https://sphe.stratworksresearch.com/index.php/sphe/article/view/11>.
- 11) **Hou, Y. (2020).** Real Property Tax in Local Public Finance. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*. Retrieved from <https://oxfordre.com/politics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.001.0001/acrefore-9780190228637-e-1431>.

- 12) **Morgeson, F. V., VanAmburg, D., & Mithas, S. (2019).** Misplaced trust? Exploring the structure of the e-government–citizen trust relationship. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 29(3), 474–490. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/muy052>.
- 13) **Nathan, B. C., Perez-Truglia, R., & Zentner, A. (2024).** Paying your fair share: Perceived fairness and tax compliance (No. w32588). National Bureau of Economic Research. Retrieved from <https://www.nber.org/papers/w32588>.
- 14) **Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2025).** Public Trust in Tax 2025: Asia and Beyond. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/en/about/news/announcements/2025/12/asia-leads-global-confidence-in-tax-fairness-but-trust-gaps-persist-elsewhere-in-the-world.html>.
- 15) **Osborne, S. P., Radnor, Z., & Nasi, G. (2015).** A new theory for public service management? Toward a (public) service-dominant approach. *American Review of Public Administration*, 45(2), 135–158. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074012466935>.
- 16) **Provincial Government of Davao Del Sur (2025).** Citizen’s Charter 2025 (1st Edition). Retrieved from <https://davaodelsur.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Citizens-Charter-2025-1st-Edition.pdf>.
- 17) **Samantela, S. S., & Maquiling, K. S. M. (2024).** Examining institutional challenges of land value capture: the case of implementing land-based Taxes in the Philippines. *Journal of Human Ecology and Sustainability*, 2(1), 7. Retrieved from <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/340794>.
- 18) **South, L., Saffo, D., Vitek, O., Dunne, C., & Borkin, M. A. (2022).** Effective use of Likert scales in visualization evaluations: A systematic review. In *Computer Graphics Forum* (Vol. 41, No. 3, pp. 43–55). Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/cgf.14521>.
- 19) **Vartašová, A., & Červená, K. (2019).** Views on Quality of Tax Regulation in the Slovak Republic (Focused on Real Property Taxation). Vartašová, A.–Červená, K. Views on Quality of Tax Regulation in the Slovak Republic (Focused on Real Property Taxation). Praha: Leges. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3728022.
- 20) **Watkins, M. W. (2018).** Exploratory factor analysis: A guide to best practice. *Journal of black psychology*, 44(3), 219–246. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0095798418771807>.
- 21) **Zaragoza, S. M., & Caelian, M. V. (2020).** Fiscal implication of agrarian reform program to the real property tax collection in Negros Occidental. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 3(3), 85–94. Retrieved from <https://philssj.org/index.php/main/article/view/263>